

Demonstration of of Zinc solubilising bacteria in Paddy in selected zinc deficient soils of Dharmapuri district

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Abstract

Among the micronutrients iron, manganese, zinc, copper and molybdenum zinc is found to be predominantly deficient throughout the country. Zinc is an imperative micronutrient required for optimum plant growth as it is the precursor for many of the growth hormone production. Zinc solubilizing bacteria (ZSB) are potential alternatives for zinc supplementation and convert applied inorganic zinc to available forms (Zn^{2+}). In addition, the application of zinc-solubilizing bacteria as a potential biosource represents a cost-effective and alternate biofortification strategy. Zinc-solubilizing bacteria act as natural bio-fortifiers that can solubilize the unavailable form of zinc by secreting organic acids, siderophores, and other chelating compounds. It has been found from the analytical reports of soil and plants that 48.5% of the soils and 44% of the plant samples were potentially zinc-deficient. In India, zinc (Zn) is now considered as fourth most important yield limiting nutrient in agricultural crops. Zn deficiency in Indian soils is likely to increase from 49 to 63% by 2025. The deficiency of zinc was found in more than fifty per cent of Tamil Nadu soil. In Paddy, Zn deficiency causes multiple symptoms that usually appear 2 to 3 weeks after transplanting (WAT) rice seedlings; leaves develop brown blotches and streaks that may fuse to cover older leaves entirely, plants remain stunted and in severe cases may die, while those that recover will show substantial delay in maturity and reduction in yield. Zn deficiency has been associated with a wide range of soil conditions: high pH (>7.0), low available Zn content, prolonged submergence and low redox potential and high available P. Availability of both soil and applied zinc is higher in upland soil than in submerged soil. Soil submergence causes decrease in zinc concentration in the soil solution. Rice crop removes 30-40 g Zn per tonne of grain. Zinc deficiency in Paddy can also be overcome by 0.5 per cent of foliar application of Zn (or) as soil application of $ZnSO_4$ @ 25 kg/ha.

Key words : Zinc Solubilising Bacteria (ZSB), Paddy, Zinc deficiency

Introduction

Micronutrients play an important role in plants. Iron, Manganese, Zinc, Copper and Molybdenum are the commonly identified micronutrients. Among these Zinc (Zn) is required for the metabolism of plants, enzyme function, and ion transport. The physicochemical involvement of Zn in soil-plant systems. Consequently, inadequate Zn availability in soil is a main consideration for plant nutrition, resulting in a significant loss in production and grain nutrient content. Zinc is distributed biogeochemically in various basins. Overall, there are five distinct forms of Zn in soil: adsorbed, interchangeable, water-soluble, complex, and chelated **Figure 1**. The phyto-availability, leachability, and extractability of these Zn pools vary substantially (Alloway, 2008). The Zn levels in the soil, pH, soil texture, and the occurrence of competing cations all affect the presence of Zn in the abovementioned basins. However, the minerals, chemical structure, amount of organic matter, and pH of the soil all affect the availability of Zn (Wang *et al.*, 2014). Zn availability is influenced by soil structure; sandy loam and organic soils are more prone to Zn deficiency than clayey or silty soils . Considering all aspects, soil pH has the greatest impact on the availability of Zn in soil. A higher pH soil has less availability of Zn than a lower pH soil). Various soil characteristics, including cation exchange ability, moisture content, and electrical conductivity, can influence the Zn availability in soil (Moreno-Lora and Delgado, 2020).

Role of Zinc in Paddy:

Micronutrients are important in order to help rice reach its full potential and zinc (Zn) is the most commonly deficient micronutrient both in rice and in soils. From an agronomic perspective, zinc is important to rice for a number of reasons:

Nitrogen assimilation and protein metabolism – Approximately 10% of proteins in plants require Zn for structural function and integrity. Low Zn supply limits the rice plant's ability to convert amino acids to proteins. Additionally, the rate of protein synthesis is drastically reduced in Zn-deficient plants.

Auxin metabolism – Zn deficiency causes reduced auxin levels, leading to little leaf syndrome, stunted growth and reduced shoot elongation. An example is indole acetic acid (IAA). Indole requires Zn to produce tryptophan which leads to IAA. Reduced Zn leads to higher stress responses, causing production of more free radicals, leading to the degradation of IAA.

Membrane structure, function and maintenance – Zinc deficiency can cause chlorosis by allowing the breaking down of chlorophyll.

Carbohydrate metabolism

Zinc also helps in carbohydrate metabolism

Figure 1. Strategies to enhance Zn uptake in plants.

Materials and Methods:

Field trials were conducted in the district of Dharmapuri. The trials were conducted in five different villages viz., Bairnaickenpatty, Ganapatty, Papparapatty, Gettur, Seriyampatty. The rice variety chosen was ADT 39. The field was applied with recommended dose of fertilizer. The soils were found to be deficient in zinc. The treatments were T₁ - Control (Without applying any of the biofertilizer), T₂. RDF + With Azospirillum alone and T₃ - RDF + Azospirillum + ZSB. The FLD trials were replicated thrice in each village.

Application of Zinc to Paddy crop:

Seed treatment:

Zinc Deficient Soils: Along with existing recommended biofertilizers, seed treatment is required for one hectare with 1 kg of zinc solubilizing bacterium using rice gruel, shade dry for 30 minutes before sowing.

Main field application

Zinc Deficient Soils: Along with existing recommended biofertilizers (Azospirillum), 2 kg each zinc solubilizing bacterium with 25 kg of FYM and 25 kg of sand and broadcast uniformly before transplanting.

Application of Liquid formulation of Zinc solubilizing bacteria :

Zinc Deficient Soils: Along with existing recommended biofertilizers (Azospirillum), seeds should be treated with liquid formulation of ZSB which is required for one hectare with 125 ml of zinc solubilizing bacterium shade dry for 30 minutes before sowing

Parameters recorded

The grain yield and straw yield were recorded in the front-line demonstration trials conducted at five different villages of the Dharmapuri district.

Results and Discussion

The Zinc Solubilising Bacteria (ZSB) was applied to the paddy crop along with other recommended dose of biofertilizer (i.e) Azospirillum. The yield was recorded as grain yield and straw yield. The grain yield and straw yield obtained in different villages were recorded as in table.1.

Table 1. Effect of Zinc Solubilizing Bacteria on Grain and straw yield of ADT 39 Paddy variety in Dharmapuri district (Mean values)

Villages	Grain yield (kg/ha)			Straw yield (kg/ha)		
	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃
Bairnaickenpatty	4450	4625	4800	8050	8100	8200
Ganapatty	4525	4700	4900	8100	8150	8250
Papparapatty	4650	4800	5025	8150	8200	8300
Gettur	4600	4750	5000	8075	8125	8250
Seriyampatty	4750	4900	5150	8125	8225	8300
Mean	4595	4755	4975	8100	8160	8260

T₁ - Control (Farmers practice - without applying any biofertilizer)

T₂ - RDF +Azospirillum alone T₃ - RDF + Azospirillum + ZSB

The results of the experiment showed that the highest grain yield (4975 kg/ha) was obtained in the treatment T₃ which received RDF + Azospirillum + ZSB followed by T₂ (4755 kg/ha) which received RDF + Azospirillum alone. The straw yield was also recorded to be higher in T₃. But there was no significant difference. The increase recorded in yield could be attributed to higher mobilization of Zn by Zn solubilizing bacteria. Mader *et al.* (2011) also stated an increase of 23% in rice yield obtained due to the application of ZSB. The bacterial isolates would have induced IAA production, a phytohormone responsible for increasing the length of the root hairs which could promote better absorption of nutrients from the soil. According to Volkmar and Bremer (1998) rapid establishment of roots including elongation of primary roots or proliferation of lateral/adventitious roots is advantageous for young seedlings as it increases their ability to explore the soil to easily obtain water and nutrients.

Thus, in the present study the ZSB has an effective role in increasing the grain and straw yield of the paddy crop in the five villages of Dharmapuri district.

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